

A Comparative Study of Simulation Tools for Ad hoc Networks

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Abstract

Performance analysis of computer networks is becoming increasingly important as networks grow in size. An approach to simulation is often very helpful. For validating any research idea prior to implementation, network simulation tools are used. For all researchers, regardless of the field of research, simulators offer a way to analyze the design. The performance of existing or new algorithms and protocols is tested via network simulators. A lot of network simulators exist but this work only covered simulation tools that can simulate ad hoc networks. Most existing work are on MANET, this work highlight simulators for other ad hoc networks like VANET, WSN, WMN and many more. Simulation tools for ad hoc network compared in this work include GloMoSim, JiST / SWANS, J-Sim, MATLAB / Simulink, NetSim, Ns2, Ns3, OMNeT++, OPNET and QualNet. These tools are either commercial or open source. Reviews on areas of strength, operating system supported and technologies supported where done. Also their degree of usability were reviewed and recommendations presented.

Keywords: Ad hoc, MANET, VANET, WSN, WMN, Simulator, NS3; Network

1.0 Introduction

Ad Hoc is a Latin phrase that means "for this purpose," and it is a term that is frequently used to describe solutions that are created on the fly for a specific purpose. Ad hoc networks form when devices connect and communicate with one another and does not require the use of a router or a wireless base station in computer networking. (Christensson, 2006)

For example, you could build a network of ad hoc networks between your computer and your friend's laptop to transfer your file to the laptop of your friend. The Ethernet crossover cable or the wireless cards of computers can be used to communicate with other devices. You can set up a multi hop ad hoc network to transfer data via various nodes if you need to share the files with more than one computer. An ad hoc network is one that is spontaneously formed when devices connect and communicate with each other.

Ad hoc networks are mainly wireless local wireless networks (LANs). Instead of using a base station or access points, such as Wi-Fi LANs for data transfer coordination, the devices communicate directly with one another. By determining the route with the routing algorithm and transferring data on other devices, each device is involved in a routing activity.

The network is ad hoc because it lacks pre-existing infrastructure such as routers in wired networks or access points in managed (infrastructure) wireless networks. Instead, each node is involved with data routing to other nodes, so it is determined, based on network connectivity and the routing algorithm in use, this makes nodes transmit data dynamically.

Previously, network testbeds were the defacto means for testing network. It came with a lot of challenges. Simulators are not affected by any of the testbed flaws. More precisely, because simulators allow the network to be managed as a whole, they are much easier to use and monitor. Furthermore, because experiments are described as scenarios files, they can be replicated. The simulated network's size is only limited by the computational power available. Due to the complexity of ad hoc networks, simulation is a difficult problem to solve. To improve their accuracy, speed, scalability, and usability, simulators employ a variety of techniques. (Kabir et al., 2014)

2.0 Classifications of Ad Hoc Networks

Depending upon the nature of its applications, ad-hoc networks can be classed in various types. The following are the most important ad hoc networks

2.1 MANET: stands for **M**obile **A**d hoc **N**etwork. Each MANET device has the freedom to move independently, thus frequently changing its links with other devices. Each traffic must be forwarded to its own destinations, and thus must be a router. Each unit is equipped to maintain the information required for proper road transport, as an important challenge in the construction of a MANET (Dorathy & Chandrasekaran, 2018). This becomes harder with the increase in MANET scale due to

1. the desire to route packets to / via any node;
2. the percentage of overhead traffic needed to maintain the status of real-time routing;
3. each node has its own route capacities, independent and unaware of other needs; and
4. everyone needs a limited bandwidth of communication, such as a section of the radio spectrum. These networks may be connected to the larger internet or can operate on their own. They may contain one or more transceivers between nodes. This creates a dynamic, independent topology.

2.2 VANET: The **V**ehicular **A**d hoc **N**etwork (VANET) is a new type of MANET. The VANET is used on the road, with vehicles acting as mobile nodes. VANET applications such as active security and intelligent transportation require appropriate vehicle-to-vehicle communication technology, particularly routing technology. (Gaikwad & Zaveri, 2011)

2.3 WSN: **W**ireless **S**ensor **N**etworks (WSNs) are self-configured, infrastructure-free wireless networks that monitor physical or environmental conditions such as temperature, sound, vibration, pressure, motion, or pollutants and cooperatively pass their data through the network to a central location or sink where the data can be observed and analyzed. A sink, also known as a base station, serves as a link between users and the network. By pumping queries and collecting results from the sink, one can retrieve required information from the network. A wireless sensor network typically consists of hundreds of thousands of sensor nodes. Radio signals allow the sensor nodes to communicate with one another. Sensing and computing devices, radio transceivers, and power components are all included in a wireless sensor node. Individual nodes in a wireless sensor network (WSN) are resource constrained by design: their processing speed, storage capacity, and communication bandwidth are all limited. After being deployed, the sensor nodes are responsible for self-organizing an appropriate network infrastructure, which often includes multi-hop communication. The onboard sensors then begin collecting data of interest. In addition to responding to "control site" queries, wireless devices

also perform certain instructions or provide sensing samples. The sensor nodes can operate in either a continuous or event-driven mode. To obtain location and positioning information, the Global Positioning System (GPS) and local positioning algorithms can be used. (Matin & Islam, 2012)

2.4 WMN: Wireless mesh networks (WMNs) are communication networks that include radio nodes in a mesh topology. Mesh topology is a connection between all nodes that are connected to all network nodes. The network comprises devices such as nodes, clients, routers, gateways and so on. The mesh networks are often less mobile, since redirecting is less difficult to predict the reroute results in data transmission delays. Mesh customers may be wireless, such as phones, notebooks, etc. The portals that act as transmission nodes may not be connected to the Internet. Different devices are also known as a mesh cloud as they go through a single network. WMN is curative. It works best for different networks including IEEE 802.11, 802.15, 802.16 and cellular networks. WMN can work with several protocols flexibly. (Rejina Parvin, 2020)

2.5 SPAN: is referred to as Smart Phone Ad hoc Network. Towers for cellular communication can be destroyed or overloaded. Power and network connectivity can be lost in Wi-Fi hotspots. When other infrastructure is unavailable, overwhelmed, or untrustworthy, the Smart Phone Ad hoc Networking (SPAN) project turns mobile phones and tablets into routers to provide an alternative means of disseminating information. (The MITRE Corporation, 2014)

3.0 Review of Relevant Literatures

In this section, relevant literatures on simulation tools for ad hoc networks were reviewed.

Hogie et al., (2006), mentioned that numerous tools exist for MANETs simulation, including ns-2 and GloMoSim which are the two most popular ones. Highlight of features that a state-of-the-art simulators should have to depict how accurate MANET simulators are includes granularity, mobility model, radio propagation model and simulation size.

Mehta et al., (2010), in this paper, eight most “widely used” network and system simulators and their strengths and weaknesses were discussed based on a couple of papers and a surveys. Then, the results of a survey of recent research publications on performance evaluation of networks were used to show that the majority of results of simulation studies of wireless networks published in technical literature have many pitfalls/issues.

Salem & Awwad (2014), in their survey for network simulation tools highlighted that MANET can be tested using the analytical method, testbeds, emulators and simulators. Some simulation tools highlighted by their [work are NS2, NS3, GloMoSim and OMNeT++.

Kang et al., (2016) presented a comprehensive survey on current network simulators for new emerging research area, three-dimensional wireless ad hoc and sensor networks that are represented by airborne ad hoc networks and underwater sensor networks by reviewing major existing simulators as well as presenting their main features.

Xia et al., (2016) designed a new wireless ad hoc network simulator, called Time Step-based Wireless Ad hoc Network Simulator (TimSim). It is intended to facilitate the migration of simulation code to real devices via providing useful APIs with real device driver. they used a discrete event processor with time step-based feature as the simulating engine, and the data can be transmitted in bit-level. A unique feature of TimSim is its ability to support the simulation of multi-thread programming.

Dorathy & Chandrasekaran, (2018) reviewed several simulation tools for mobile ad hoc network. Some of the tools reviewed are OPNET (optimized Network Engineering Tool), NS-

2 (Network Simulator version 2), OMNET++ (Objective Modular NETWORK Testbed in C++), GloMoSim (Global Mobile Information System Simulator), QualNet, NetSim (Network Simulator), JiST/SWANS (Java in Simulation Time/ Scalable Wireless Network Simulator), J-Sim (Java-based simulation) and NS-3 (Network Simulator Version 3). Comparison of their strengths and weaknesses was justified by this work.

4.0 Ad Hoc Network Simulation Tools

Network Simulation Software simulates the behavior of a modeled network in a repeatable and controllable environment for a variety of testing purposes. It makes use of simulation to figure out how different changes will affect performance during a future configuration or application deployment.

By the time of this research, some network simulation tools reviewed in previous works have become old and obsolete without new update. We shall try to review simulation tools that are current and up-to-date.

4.1 GloMoSim: Global Mobile Information System Simulator (GloMoSim) is a network protocol simulator that can be used to simulate both wireless and wired networks. It was created with the help of Parsec's parallel discrete-event simulation capability. Currently, GloMoSim supports protocols for a purely wireless network. The simulation protocols are compiled using the Parsec compiler.

Parsec is a C-based simulation language, developed by the Parallel Computing Laboratory at UCLA, for sequential and parallel execution of discrete-event simulation models. In GloMoSim simulator projects, a visual programming environment called PAVE is developed to support the visual design of PARSEC programs or the configuration of a simulation model using the predefined component library. GloMoSim has a platform-independent Visualization Tool because it is written in Java.

Model of layers are implemented in GloMoSim. In the network layer, GloMoSim can model Bellman-Ford, FSR, OSPF, DSR, WRP, LAR, AODV routing protocols. GLOMOSIM can support a two-node mobility model, with each node moving according to a random waypoint model. Secondly, the random drunken model is a term used in GLOMOSIM to describe other mobility models.

It has wide models for ad hoc networks which includes MANET (Proactive, reactive and hybrid routing protocols), WSN, VANET, DTN (Delay tolerant Network) and WMN.

4.2 JiST/SWANS: refers to Java in Simulation Time/ Scalable Wireless Ad hoc Network Simulator. JiST is a discrete event simulation engine that runs on top of a standard Java virtual machine. It's a prototype for virtual machine-based simulation, a new general-purpose approach to building discrete event simulators that combines traditional systems and language-based simulator designs. The simulation platform that results is surprisingly efficient. In terms of both time and memory consumption, it outperforms existing highly optimized simulation runtimes. JiST, for example, has twice the raw event throughput of the Parsec engine, which is based on C, and supports process-oriented simulation with a fraction of the memory.

The JiST approach is also inherently flexible, allowing for important cross-cutting program transformations and optimizations to be performed invisibly. A key benefit is that simulation code written on JiST does not need to be written in a domain-specific language designed specifically for writing simulations, nor does it need to be littered with special-purpose system calls and call-backs to support runtime

simulation functionality. JiST, on the other hand, transforms an existing virtual machine into a simulation platform by embedding simulation time semantics in the byte-code. Thus, JiST simulations are written in Java, compiled using a regular Java compiler, and run over a standard, unmodified virtual machine.

SWANS is a JiST-based wireless network simulator with scalability. It was created primarily because existing network simulation tools are insufficient for current research needs, and its success serves as proof of concept for the virtual machine-based approach to simulator development. SWANS is organized as a collection of self-contained software components that can be combined to create complete wireless network or sensor network configurations. It has similar capabilities to ns2 and GloMoSim, but can simulate much larger networks. SWANS leverages the JiST design to achieve high simulation throughput, save memory, and run standard Java network applications over simulated networks. In addition, SWANS implements a data structure, called hierarchical binning, for efficient computation of signal propagation.

- 4.3 **J-Sim:** J-Sim is an open-source Java-based component-based compositional network simulation environment. J-Sim is built on top of an autonomous component architecture, which is a component-based software architecture (ACA). J-Sim is an application development environment based on the Autonomous Component Architecture (ACA), a component-based software architecture. The Tcl scripting language is used to create the components. J-Sim uses a generalized packet switched network model. This model is composed of basic, abstract components extracted from the Internet, and hence the name Internetworking Simulation Platform (INET) (Sobeih et al., 2005)
- 4.4 **MATLAB / Simulink:** MATLAB combines a desktop environment tuned for iterative analysis and design processes with a programming language that expresses matrix and array mathematics directly. It includes the Live Editor for creating scripts that combine code, output, and formatted text in an executable notebook (MathWorks, 2021).

When you use MATLAB and Simulink together, you combine textual and graphical programming to design your system in a simulation environment. Simulink has a lot of capabilities which includes discrete-event simulation. Discrete-event simulation with Simulink provides capabilities for analyzing and optimizing event-driven communications and operations using hybrid system models, agent-based models, and state charts. Within this integrated modeling and data analysis environment, you can:

- Model process flows, perform capacity planning, and optimize supply chains for manufacturing and operations
- Simulate event-driven processes such as mission plans with autonomous agents or the stages of a manufacturing process
- Customize queues, routing algorithms, processing delays, and prioritization schemes
- Analyze and optimize end-to-end latencies, throughput, packet loss, and other performance characteristics of communication networks
- Design distributed control systems, hardware architectures, and sensor and communication networks for aerospace, automotive, and electronics applications

- Simulate hybrid systems containing time-based, event-based, and agent-based components

4.5 **NetSim:** Network Simulator (NetSim) accelerate network R&D and reduce your time-to-publish. This Simulator is one of the best around the industry now. It comes with source C code and allows users to

- Design new protocols and technologies, as well as evaluate changes to existing ones
- Test and demonstrate designs in realistic scenarios
- Optimize protocol and application performance
- Study the effect of real devices and transmit live traffic using NetSim Emulator. Emulator combines the real and virtual worlds to create scenarios that cannot be achieved in a lab environment.

It has the following features.

- Easy to use GUI allows users to simply drag and drop devices, links and applications
- Results dashboard provides appealing simulation performance reports with tables & graphs
- Inbuilt graphing with extensive formatting (axes, colours, zoom, titles etc)
- Wide range of technologies including the latest in IOT, WSN, MANET, Cognitive Radio, 802.11 n/ac, TCP, BIC/CUBIC, Rate adaptation with packet and event tracing
- R & D projects available with source C code and documentation to easily develop / improve on
- Online debug capability and ability to "watch" all variables. Run animation in parallel for immediate visual feedback.
- External interfaces to external software like MATLAB, SUMO and Wireshark.
- Researchers trust NetSim for simulating MANET radios, emulating huge distribution networks or simply presenting a report to management. A team of NetSim engineers continuously verify NetSim results through hundreds of tests every day.

4.6 **Ns2 (Network Simulator 2):** Ns is a discrete event simulator designed specifically for network research. Ns provides extensive support for simulation of TCP, routing, and multicast protocols over wired and wireless (local and satellite) networks. NS2 is the version 2 of Ns a project supported by DARPA and many other organizations.

4.7 **Ns3 (Network Simulator 3):** ns-3 is a discrete-event network simulator for Internet systems that is primarily intended for academic and research purposes. Ns-3 is open-source software that is freely available for research, development, and use under the GNU GPLv2 license.

The ns-3 project is dedicated to developing a robust simulation core that is well-documented, simple to use and debug, and meets the needs of the entire simulation workflow, from simulation configuration to trace collection and analysis.

Furthermore, the ns-3 software infrastructure encourages the creation of simulation models that are realistic enough to allow ns-3 to be used as a real-time network emulator that is connected to the real world and that reuses many existing real-world protocol implementations.

- 4.8 **OMNeT++:** OMNeT++ is a C++ simulation library and framework that is primarily used to create network simulators. It is extensible, modular, and component-based. The term "network" refers to both wired and wireless communication networks, as well as on-chip networks, queueing networks, and other types of networks. Model frameworks, which are developed as separate projects, provide domain-specific functionality such as support for sensor networks, wireless ad-hoc networks, Internet protocols, performance modeling, photonic networks, and so on. OMNeT++ includes an Eclipse-based integrated development environment, a graphical runtime environment, and a number of other features.
- 4.9 **Riverbed OPNET:** Riverbed OPNET Modeler Suite is a protocol and technology suite with a sophisticated development environment. OPNET Modeler analyzes networks by modeling all network types and technologies (including VoIP, TCP, OSPFv3, MPLS, IPv6, and others) and comparing the impact of different technology designs on end-to-end behavior. OPNET Modeler Suite enables you to test and demonstrate technology designs before they are put into production, increase network R&D productivity, develop proprietary wireless protocols and technologies, and evaluate enhancements to standards-based protocols.
- 4.10 **QualNet:** QualNet can run accurate, at-scale network simulations in less than a second, has a large library of network models, and offers a set of tools for scenario creation, network visualization, and analysis. It provides high-speed, large-scale simulations that allow users to run through a variety of scenarios in a short amount of time and model thousands of nodes to simulate their network using parallel computation techniques.

QualNet makes it simple to create comprehensive network models and generate statistics that reflect actual (or anticipated) performance. QualNet includes three user-friendly design, visualization, and analysis modes, allowing engineers to build models, evaluate network functions, and design new protocols in the same package.

- Design Mode – Using an intuitive point-and-click drag-and-drop graphical user interface, create virtual network models by configuring the terrain, network, and functional parameters, as well as any other details.
- Visualization Mode – Perform in-depth visualization and analysis of a network scenario created in Design Mode, including data packet flow, dynamic graphs, and real-time statistics.
- Analyzer Mode – A statistical graphing tool that displays hundreds of metrics in reports, graphs, or exports to compare simulations and what-if scenarios of multiple experiments.

4.0 Comparison and Discussion

About 10 ad hoc network simulators has been selected and surveyed above. Here, Comparison the various distinct features of these selected ad hoc network simulator is done. This Comparison is in three categories namely;

- Comparison based on year founded
- Comparison based on Operating system (O.S.) platform and license and
- Comparison based on ad hoc technologies and protocols supported.

Table 1 Comparison of simulators based on year founded.

Simulators	Founded	Headquarter	Website	Name of Organization
GloMoSim	1998	UCLA	http://pcl.cs.ucla.edu/projects/glomosis	Parallel computing laboratory Team
JiST/SWANS	2004	Cornell University	http://jist.ece.cornell.edu/index.html	JiST / SWANS Project Team
J-Sim.	1999	University of Illinois	https://sites.google.com/site/jsimofficial/Home http://j-sim.cs.uiuc.edu/	Next Generation Software program
MATLAB/ Simulink	1984	1 Apple Hill Drive Natick, MA 01760-2098	https://www.mathworks.com/solutions/discrete-event-simulation.html	MathWorks
NetSim	2005	Bangalore, India	https://www.tetcos.com/	TETCOS
Ns2	1989	4676 Admiralty Way, Suite 1001, Marina del Rey, CA 90292	http://sourceforge.net/projects/nsnam/	Information Sciences Institute, University of Southern California
Ns3	2010	University of Washington.	https://www.nsnam.org/	Nsnam Project Team
OMNeT++	2016		https://omnetpp.org/intro/	OpenSim Ltd
OPNET	1986	Bethesda, Maryland, USA	https://web.archive.org/web/20140224212321/http://www.riverbed.com/ http://opnet.com	Riverbed Technology
QualNet	1999	6167 Bristol Parkway, Suite 400 Culver City, CA 90230 USA	https://www.scalable-networks.com/products/qualnet-network-simulation-software/	SCALABLE Network Technologies, Inc.

Table 2 Comparison based on O. S. platform and license.

Simulators	Operating System Supported	Programming Language	GUI Support	Support Service / Documentation	Extension Integration	License
GloMoSim	Linux, Windows	C / Parsec	Poor GUI Support	Poor	Yes	Open Source
JiST/SWANS	Linux, Mac OS, Windows	Java/Tel	Poor GUI Support	Fair	Yes	Open Source
J-Sim.	Linux, Mac OS, Windows	Java	Poor GUI Support	Fair	Yes	Open Source
MATLAB/ Simulink	Linux, Mac OS, Windows	C++ / MATHLAB	Excellent GUI	Excellent	Yes	Commercial
NetSim	Windows	C / Java	Excellent GUI	Excellent	Yes	Commercial
Ns2	Linux, Mac OS	C++ / OTcl	Poor GUI (Command Line)	Poor	Yes	Open Source
Ns3	Linux, Mac OS	C++ / Python	Poor GUI (Command Line)	Good	Yes	Open Source
OMNeT++	Linux, Mac OS, Windows	C++ / NED	Good GUI	Good	Yes	Freeware
OPNET	Linux, Windows	C++	Excellent GUI		Yes	Commercial

QualNet	Linux, Mac OS, Windows	Parsec	Excellent GUI	Good	Yes	Commercial
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Table 3 Comparison based on adhoc technologies and protocols supported

Simulators	Ad hoc Technologies supported	Mobility	Application Layer Protocols	Transport Layer Protocols	(Network Layer Protocols
GloMoSim	MANET, VANET	Random Way Point, File-based Dead Reckoning Group, Pedestrian	CBR, Telnet, Web	TCP, UDP, FTP, DBS	Distributed Bellman Ford, Flooding, Fisheye, DSR, DSDV, WRP, LAR, DREAM, NS-DSDV
JiST/SWANS	MANET, VANET	Random way point, Random walk, Teleport	CBR, FTP, VBR	TCP, UDP	ZRP, AODV, DSR
J-Sim.	MANET, VANET, WSN	Random way point, SDF trace-based, Model	CBR, FTP, VBR	TCP, UDP	Shortest path, Spanning tree, OSPF, DVR, DVMRP, DSR, AODV
MATLAB/ Simulink	MANET, SPAN, VANET, WSN, WMN	Uses Models	FTP, HTTP	TCP, UDP	Routing Protocols generally for all Ad hoc Network
NetSim	MANET, VANET, WSN	Random way point, Random walk	Voice, Video, FTP, Database, HTTP, Email	TCP, UDP	AODV, DSR, OLSR, ZRP, RPL, IPv6,
Ns2	MANET, VANET	Random Direction, Random walk	FTP, Telnet, Web, CBR, VRB	TCP, UDP	DSR, AODV, DSDV
Ns3	MANET, SPAN, VANET, WSN, WMN	Random Direction, Random walk, Random way point, 3D GM	CBR, FTP, VBR	TCP, UDP	IPv4, IPv6, OSLR, AODV, DSR, DSDV
OMNeT++	MANET, VANET, WSN, WMN	Random Walk, Turtle Group, Pedestrian,	Telnet	TCP, UDP, SCTP	IPv4, IPv6, OSPF, BGP
OPNET	MANET, VANET, WSN, WMN	Random Way Point, Vector	CBR, FTP, VBR	TCP, UDP	IPv4, IPv6, ICMP, ICMP v6, OSPF, RIPv1, RIPv2
QualNet	MANET, VANET, WSN, WMN	Random way point, Random walk	CBR, FTP, VBR	TCP, UDP, rtp, rsvp, mpls, DiffServ	Distributed Bellman-Ford, OSPFv2, RIPv2, BGP, Flooding, Fisheye, DSR, DSDV, WRP, LAR, AODV

5.0 Conclusion

Simulation has become the best way to test a network performance or its corresponding protocols to know how it will actually perform in real life situation. These simulation tools compared above has shown some areas of strength and weakness, therefore reserachers should decide which type of simulation tool to use based on the nature of adhoc network you wish to simulate, size of network to be simulated, type of project (Academic or commercial), type of sponsorship (Individual or corporate) and chod choice of Operating system platform you wish to use in simulation.

Use any of OPNET, GloMoSim, QualNet, NetSim, JiST/SWANS and NS-3 simulators for large network simulation. NS-2 or J-Sim can be used to simulate small networks. The

documentation of the open source simulators is poor. Good documentation is available for commercial simulators. So a specific simulation tool can be selected based on the requirements of the research. However, no simulation tool fulfills all the requirement. NetSim as a wonderful simulator, easy to use, excellent graphical User interface, quality user support but don't support all protocols in an ad hoc network by default. Some protocols need to be custom-made if you want it simulated on NetSim.

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